

Biological Resources Certifications Schemes

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Type

- R** Document report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.
- Other**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN** Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- CI** Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 1001/844/EC

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Publishable Executive Summary

BioReCer aims to ensure the environmental performance and traceability of biological feedstock used by the bio-based industries. This will be executed through the deployment of guidelines to strengthen current certification schemes by including new criteria that align with EU taxonomy and EU corporate due diligence regulations. Within this approach, the added value, the use, as well as the social acceptance of bioproducts will be increased.

With this objective in mind, BioReCer is structured in three main technological pillars:

1. development of a multidimensional assessment framework and a digital BioReCer ICT-tool (BIT) for the aggregated and collaborative analysis of biological feedstocks and their associated supply chains;
2. creation of a BioReCer Innovation Ecosystem Living-Lab (BRIE-LL) following a multi-agent approach and the testing of this framework in four bio-based supply chain case studies,
3. using all generated knowledge to complement current certification schemes by including new sustainability and traceability criteria, and ensure their applicability at EU and global scale.

The transition to a bio-based economy is expected to deliver substantial environmental, societal and economic benefits. For this, BioReCer assesses the impact of current and adapted certification schemes on (end-)users and bio-based industries stakeholders' willingness to pay (WTP) along with acceptance of value chains from novel biological feedstocks (including residual feedstock and waste(water)) by industries and consumers. The project designs and develops a multidimensional assessment framework to analyse the environmental performance of biological resources and traceability. This framework will be subsequently validated in four case studies which will allow for the applicability in a wide range of bio-based value chains. This approach is unfolded by the joint creation of two levels of interaction: a physical one through the creation of a BioResources Stakeholders Platform (BRSP) and a "digital" one through a BioReCer ICT tool (BIT).

This document is the mid-term report on all executed communication and dissemination activities and measures between M1 and M18 that target different stakeholder groups (including the BRSP) in order to maximise the project's reach and success.

1 Introduction

This document is the mid-term report on BioReCer communication and dissemination (C&D) activities and gives an overview of the BioReCer stakeholder groups (including the BRSP) that had been targeted by these C&D measures. Also, it lists all performed C&D measures between M1 and M18 and evaluates their impact by aligning their outcomes with the KPIs that were defined in D8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan. In contrast to the Communication and Dissemination Plan, the mid-term report does not provide a strategy for concise C&D, but informs and evaluates the past measures and describes joined activities with related projects and the status of deliverables. Furthermore, an overview about upcoming C&D measures is given at the end of this document.

2 Stakeholder Engagement

Due to its inclusive and interactive stakeholder approach, BioReCer relies on a comprehensive stakeholder analysis for the set-up of the BRSP. Detailed stakeholder identification and analysis are therefore a focus point in WP2 and WP4. Besides, also for the four case studies WP6 identified relevant stakeholders.

2.1 Stakeholder Groups

From the beginning of the project several stakeholder groups were identified, classified and are monitored throughout the project runtime, that are being targeted with tailor-made communication and dissemination measures (see GA, results and activities of WP4 and stakeholder analysis in D8.1 Dissemination and Communication Plan). All partners personally addressed their own contacts, promoted the strong stakeholder aspect of the project with website articles, LinkedIn activities and project booths at conferences and thus invited stakeholders to join the BRSP.

The stakeholders relevant for BioReCer are biomass producers, members of the biobased industries, holders of certification schemes and standardisation bodies, the scientific community, policy makers and consumer organisations/associations, the press and the general public.

2.2 Members of the BRSP

A strong focus of BioReCer lies on stakeholders from the four case study countries (Greece, Italy, Spain and Sweden). However, stakeholders from all other (EU) countries are relevant for the BRSP. Currently (2nd February 2024), the BRSP consists of 85 members from 69 different companies/institutions. The gender ratio is almost balanced with 43 men and 41 women (one stakeholder address did not specify a person but a company). The members of the BRSP have either a single or several interests and cover a broad spectrum of competences: 23 persons stated that they are members of the biobased industry, 20 are biomass producers, 7 are certification bodies, 14 belong to consumer associations, 6 are part of trade bodies, 12 belong to institutions such as consortia or associations other than consumer associations, 14 identified as policy makers, and 19 belong to none of the above. 35 stakeholders expressed interest in case study 2 (urban waste streams), 55 are interested in case study 3 (agricultural waste) and 30 in case study 4 (forestry). 16 persons did not express interest in one or more specific case study but are generally interested in all of them.

The stakeholders from the BRSP originate from 14 different countries, most of them from the four different case studies (14 ES, 11 SE, 22 IT, 25 GR), but also from other EU countries, i.e. Germany (8), Austria (1), Cyprus (1) and France (1). Also, two persons from EU facilities and 1 person from UK participated. There are also several persons originating from outside of Europe in the BRSP (South Africa, Kenya, Indonesia, Colombia).

All persons interested to become members of the BRSP have the possibility to either register via the website or by filling-in an offline application form. Before becoming a member of the BRSP, everybody has to agree to terms and conditions and the data protection regulation.

Figure 1: BRSP application forms: On website (left) and in paper form (right).

2.3 Tailor-made Measures

Several measures have already taken place between M1 and 18 (see next chapters) and more are upcoming. These include measures that target all stakeholder groups, e.g. the project video, the brochure, the website, Social Media postings. However, there were also measures targeting specific stakeholder groups:

Members of the BRSP and stakeholders of the four case studies:

- The stakeholders factsheet in different languages to promote the BRSP in the four case study countries.
- Focus Group Discussions (in English or the local language) for each case study (the outcome of all FGDs and information on the participants can be found in D4.1 Report on the whole development of the BRSP)
- National Stakeholders Meetings as in-person events. The first one had been taken place in October 2023 as side event to the BioReCer Consortium Meeting in Thessaloniki. It informed the Greek stakeholders on the development of BioReCer. The next national meeting is planned in person for June 2024 as side event to the Consortium Meeting in Sweden.
- Annual Stakeholders Meetings: The first annual stakeholders meeting had been taken place online in November 2024. It informed the participants about the BioReCer progress, circular economy indicators and the EU’s green claims directive.

Figure 2: Two-sided Stakeholders Factsheet available online (website) and in paper.

Figure 3: Banners to announce the stakeholder event in Greece (left) and the first annual stakeholders meeting (right)

Policy makers in general are specifically targeted by the First Policy Brief on “Valorisation and Use of Biological Waste and By-Products Supports the European Bioeconomy” which was due in M18 as D8.6.

All partners published Social Media posts to target their own follower community/their clientele. Furthermore, different stakeholder groups are targeted by posting and reposting in specific LinkedIn groups.

Furthermore, by participating or organising events, specific stakeholder groups are reached. For example, the European bioplastics community was reached with a project booth at the ECB23 in Berlin, and UNI organised an online training on standards in cooperation with the related project Star4bbs. EGM will also participate in Pollutec Paris in November 2024 to present their BioReCer results to experts in the field of waste management.

Figure 4: Banner to announce the participation of BioReCer at the EBC23 with a shared project booth with the related Horizon Europe project 3-CO.

2.4 Certificate of Participation and Vignette

NOVA designed certificates of appreciation and a vignette in the BioReCer colour code to recognise the participation and engagement of stakeholders in the Greek Stakeholders Event in October 2023. These certificates and vignettes (that can also be used for Social Media postings by the stakeholders to display their participation in the BRSP) are also going to be awarded to the Swedish, Spanish and Italian stakeholders in the upcoming in-person stakeholders meetings.

Figure 5: Blanco certificate of participation for the stakeholders participating in the Greek stakeholder event and vignette that can be used for Social Media postings.

3 Communication Activities (M1 to M18)

3.1 Project Identity

A cohesive and appealing project identity (ID) and a project logo were created in collaboration with all partners. This ID and the logo were subsequently used to develop templates (.txt and .ppt) for reports, deliverables, milestones and presentations, and to create branded materials to standardise external communication and make the project recognisable. These branded materials include the brochure, the stakeholders factsheet, the website, a roll-up banner, zoom backgrounds, name tags and event banners. The ID and the logo will also be utilised for upcoming measures.

Euradia also prepared sets of diverse imagery based on the project ID that was provided to the partners to be used for Social Media postings or for other BioReCer-related measures that require imagery.

Figure 6: BioReCer project logo (left), branded imagery by EURADIA (middle) and one of two branded BioReCer Zoom backgrounds (right).

3.2 Communication and Dissemination Plan (D8.1)

The CDP corresponds to D8.1 and was due in M6. It presents an impactful strategy to address identified stakeholder and target groups and lists executed measures. The CDP includes activities, channels and instruments for communication and dissemination that the consortium is using in order to ensure high visibility, information accessibility and effective promotion of the project and generated results throughout the entire project duration. In this context, the CDP serves as a guideline and reference framework to guide and evaluate the impact of communication and dissemination activities that have been carried out. This is achieved by evaluating set key performance indicators (KPI) and by establishing new ones. In case the measures fail to meet the defined goals and the respective KPIs, alternative paths and solutions are suggested in the mid-term and final report on C&D measures.

Figure 7: BioReCer ppt template (left) and deliverable template (right).

3.3 Internal Communication

Internal communication is guaranteed by the common use of a SharePoint via Google Drive by all members of the BioReCer consortium. Here, information on stakeholders and WP developments are shared between partners in a safe and protected platform. For communication between members of the WPs, NOVA created mailing lists that are frequently updated if members leave or enter a respective WP. Also, all WPs organise frequent online WP meetings to keep all respective partners updated on the work progress and new developments. Mailing lists were also created for the project executive board (PEB) and the project managing board (PMB), as well as for the communication managers of the partners.

Furthermore, EURADIA published a first internal newsletter to inform all partners on the progress of each WP.

3.4 Gender and Diversity Aspects for External Communication

In all communication output, aspects of cultural, racial and sexual diversity were considered in the created communication and dissemination materials to ensure an appropriate representation of the broad society. All communication material created in BioReCer use non-discriminatory and inclusive language in different languages. This includes imagery with high contrast and avoiding colours that are not differentiable by colour-blind persons, hashtags in CamelCase in order to make them readable for dyslectic persons, alt-texts of imagery to make it accessible for visually impaired persons, and video subtitles for hearing impaired persons.

3.5 Website

3.5.1 Website and Website Updates

The project website equals D8.2 and was up and running in M6. More information on its set-up and the first version can be found in D8.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan. Since the launch of the first version of the website, it was continuously updated by including new subpages to the News & Media section, i.e. News, Events, Press Releases, Publications, Public Deliverables and Media and by adding a Related Projects page. Furthermore, a pop-up window for newsletter subscription, a Social Media feed and the project video are now provided. The News & Media and the Related Projects pages are continuously updated with new information on events, website articles and downloadable materials, such as the brochure, infographic and stakeholders factsheet, and new projects. The website will be continuously up-dated and maintained throughout the project duration and 5 years after the project's completion.

Figure 8: Impressions of the BioReCer website.

3.5.2 Website Statistics

The website performance is continuously monitored by the analytics tool "Matomo LogFile Analytics", which provides a multitude of relevant information about visitor statistics, visit durations and visitor locations. These analyses serve as a basis for continuous improvement and optimisation of the chosen measures and presented content of the project website. Unfortunately, during August 2023 a NOVA server was moved to a new location and did not record the website visitors, which resulted in a gap in website statistics. However, since August is a holiday month in many European countries, the gap does probably not harshly influence the general findings for the website statistics for the rest of the recording period.

Since the website launch the visits have continuously increased over time (in whole: >130,000 visits with an average visit duration of 3:35 min) and many other activities were observed, e.g., about 406,000 downloads. The peaks in visits partly correlated with social media activity, e.g., preceding the first stakeholder focus group discussions of the fish canning industry (11th May 2023) and of the forestry industry (25th of May 2023). Most

visitors originate from the United States followed by Europe (especially France and Germany) and Asia (especially Singapore, China and India).

Figure 9: Website statistics: Visits over time (top), countries of visitors (globally, lower left; Europe, lower right).

The most visited pages were the Events page (4475 page views), which in most cases was also the entry page to the website, followed by the BRSP (1847 page views), the BRSP Membership page (1769 page views), the Project page (1708 page views) and the News & Media page (1552 page views).

3.5.3 Website Articles

Since the website’s launch eight website articles (e.g. by UNI and EURADIA) were published on the project website, six of them referring to press releases by NOVA, RISE, ACN and UNITELMA.

Figure 10: Website article (left), roll-up banner (middle), infographic (right).

3.6 Roll-up banner

A roll-up banner was designed by NOVA presenting the project name, logo, funding disclaimer, the EU logo and the logos of all members of the BioReCer consortium. This banner was used for project booths and during events that were organised by BioReCer and serves as an eye-catcher during conferences and trade fairs.

3.7 Infographic

Infographics present an effective information tool, that allows to describe complex processes in a simplified, visual and structured form. Since the interconnection of the BioReCer work packages and working groups and related outcomes (i.e. BRIE-LL, BRSP, BIT and the four case studies) is very complex, it needed to be represented visually in a plausible, easy to understand and appealing way. The BioReCer infographic was created with input from the entire consortium and was published both within the project brochure and as an individual image file on the website (https://biorecer.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/23-02-09_biorecer-infographic.pdf).

Should a fifth international case study be executed, NOVA will create an updated, amended version of the current infographic.

3.8 Brochure

The project brochure informs about the objectives of BioReCer, gives background information, displays the BioReCer infographic and explains the project content and course of action. It was designed by NOVA and follows the project’s colour code and ID. It includes the EU logo, funding disclaimer, project partner logos and refers to the website via a QR code. It is available both in paper form and as pdf on the website in three different languages (English, French, Spanish). It was distributed by all partners at different occasions and via email. It is foreseen that an updated version of the brochure is designed in case an international case study will be included in BioReCer’s assessment framework.

Figure 11: BioReCer brochure.

3.9 Factsheets

A factsheet was designed by NOVA to make stakeholders aware of the BRSP and to invite them to become members. It informs about the BRSP, the goals, challenges and solutions addressed and offered by BioReCer, highlights the importance of stakeholder involvement in BioReCer, includes a short glossary on key words, lists the activities for current members of the BRSP and informs on the advantages for the different stakeholder groups when joining the BRSP. It was designed by NOVA and follows the project’s colour code and ID. It includes the EU logo, funding disclaimer, project partner logos and refers to the website via a QR code. It is available both in paper form and as pdf on the website in four different languages (English, French, Italian, Spanish). It was distributed alongside the brochure by all partners at different occasions and via email.

Besides the Stakeholders Factsheet, further factsheets will be developed to inform about organic residues (including biological waste and by-products) as feedstock, and to describe the BIT and its application to users from the BRSP. Factsheets will be provided in printed layout form and as digital versions.

3.10 Project Video

The project video equals D8.4 and was due in M18. Three different video agencies were contacted to be able to compare different offers. The video agency that was chosen offered the best prize and an infinite number of feedback loops. The script was drafted by the video agency and revised by NOVA. The final script was used by the video agency for developing a style frame and a story board which served as basis for the animation. The spoken text is also displayed as subtitles to make the video available to hearing-impaired persons and to make it accessible in environments in which the sound cannot be switched on (e.g. on the go and during travels). In every progress step, the partners were involved to provide feedback and suggestions. The final video was approved by the coordinator and all partners and was published on the project website and on YouTube (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hi5CVZpkV2k&embeds_referring_euri=https%3A%2F%2Fbiorecer.eu%2F&feature=emb_imp_woyt). The freeze images of the video were provided by the video agency and can be used as imagery for all C&D measures of BioReCer.

Figure 12: Three scenes from the BioReCer video.

3.11 Mini-interviews

Until now, two BioReCer consortium partners (Pedro Villanueva from Cetaqua and Daniela Quaggia from Active Citizenship, ACN) were interviewed by NOVA. They were both asked three short questions in order to present the partner’s company/institution to stakeholders and to elaborate on different aspects of the project from the partner’s perspective, e.g. innovation of BioReCer and potential of waste as resource, and the stakeholder involvement in the BRSP. Both interviews are accessible via the consortium page of the project website and were promoted via the project’s newsletter and Social Media. For every upcoming project newsletter more partner interviews are planned.

Figure 13: Mini-interview with Pedro Villanueva (left) and Social Media banner for promotion of the mini-interview with Daniela Quaggia (right).

3.12 Press Releases

Press releases communicate intermediate results, important milestones and extraordinary achievements to key media actors. Throughout the project duration, BioReCer will publish at least three press releases in English, which (whenever possible) will be translated into

more languages and made available to targeted audiences. All press releases are also made available on the project website.

Currently, six press releases have been published by NOVA, RISE, ACN and UNITELMA to introduce BioReCer and the project in connection with another certification project (Star4bbs). Furthermore, a press release from outside the consortium was published by Industry Intelligence Inc.: <https://www.industryintel.com/bioeconomy/news/two-new-horizon-europe-projects-star4bbs-and-biorecer-focus-on-development-of-innovative-certification-schemes-labels-for-bio-based-feedstock-aim-is-to-address-urgent-need-for-harmonization-of-schemes-increase-transparency-of-global-and-eu-trade-flows-157822417488>

All NOVA press releases are also sent out to the press via a tailor-made NOVA press mailing list and a distribution list with 349 press contacts via the press network Zimpel. All NOVA press releases are also published in the daily newsletter Renewable Carbon News and in the monthly NOVA newsletter.

Figure 14: Example of a press release by NOVA in the Renewable Carbon News (left) and the Press Release Subpage on the BioReCer website.

3.13 Newsletters

3.13.1 Newsletters Published by Partners

NOVA hosts the daily news platform Renewable Carbon News (<https://renewable-carbon.eu>) that focuses on renewable carbon and renewable material and reaches more than 300,000 monthly readers. Furthermore, NOVA as one of the leading institutes in the renewable carbon sector reaches over 3,500 subscribers with a monthly newsletter.

All press releases and all website articles published by NOVA (alone or in collaboration with EURADIA and UNI) are also distributed via these two newsletters.

All project partners are instructed to actively incorporate, communicate and disseminate BioReCer news via their specific company newsletters, and to share links of published newsletter articles with the consortium to enable sharing and further distribution among the partners' respective networks.

3.13.2 Project Newsletter

The BioReCer website offers the possibility to subscribe to the project newsletter which was already send out three times in 2023. The fourth newsletter is foreseen for March 2024.

The first project newsletter was published in September 2023. It announced the two stakeholder events (i.e. Stakeholder Event in Greece and the First Annual Stakeholders Meeting), presented the stakeholders factsheet, offered the link to an online survey and promoted the first mini-interview with Cetaqua.

The second newsletter was a special edition event newsletter send out in October 2023 to promote the two stakeholder events that had already been announced in the first newsletter.

The third newsletter was dedicated to the BRSP Stakeholders and was published in December 2023. It informed about the past stakeholder events, the consortium meeting in Thessaloniki, promoted the newly established BioReCer LinkedIn group and provided information on the past events BioReCer partners had participated in. It also promoted the second mini-interview with Active Citizenship.

The project newsletter always displays the project logo, the EU logo and the funding disclaimer.

Currently (2nd February 2024), the newsletter counts 76 subscribers. The opening rate of the newsletters were between 45 and 57%.

Figure 15: Possibility to subscribe to the project newsletter on the website (left) and clipping from the third BioReCer newsletter (right).

3.14 Non-scientific Publications

Several partners (i.e. CERTH, BETANIA, ANFACO, Gruppo CAP) published 8 non-scientific articles in magazines.

Table 1: Non-scientific articles published by BioReCer partners between M1 and 18.

Title	Link
Adapting certification schemes for biomasses and biowastes resources	https://waste-management-world.com/organic-waste/adapting-certification-schemes-for-biomasses-and-biowastes-resources/
BIORECER: El rol fundamental de los agricultores en la utilización de recursos valiosos	https://www.infoagro.com/noticias/2023/biorecer_el_rol_fundamental_de_los_agricultores_en_la_utilizacion_de_.asp
Fomentar nuevas cadenas de valor de base biológica para la biomasa y los bioresiduos	https://www.ciudadesostenible.eu/proyecto-biorecer-fomentar-nuevas-cadenas-de-valor-de-base-biologica-para-la-biomasa-y-los-biorresiduos/
Industria Conservera: Reunión Anual del Proyecto Biorecer	https://anfaco.es/?r3d=revista-industria-conservera-no-154
ANFACO-CECOPECA hosted the initial working group of the BIORECER project.	https://anfaco.es/revista/
Gruppo CAP partecipa al progetto BioReCer	https://www.serviziarete.it/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/Gruppo-CAP-partecipa-al-progetto-BioReCer_2-23.pdf
BIORECER: Optimizar todo el potencial de los recursos de biomasa y bioresiduos	https://www.residuosprofesional.com/biorecer-potencial-biomasa-biorresiduos/
Industria Conservera sectoral magazine, Dec. 22: page 54-55	https://issuu.com/anfacocopesca/docs/rev.n_150_diciembre

3.15 Policy Briefs

To ensure sufficient transfer of information on certification and sustainability of biological resources to relevant policy makers, at least two policy briefs will be created. These will include practical suggestions, recommendations and key- aspects to help policy makers to deliver successful strategies and instruments for the promotion and update of sustainable management and use of biological resources on EU level. The first policy brief of BioReCer equals D8.6 and was due in M18. It addresses the management and challenges for the utilisation of waste as resource in the EU, summarises the results from the material flow analysis performed by BioReCer and offers recommendations for policy makers that align with EU legislation. It is available on the project website and will be distributed in paper form and as pdf to respective stakeholders at different occasions. The second policy brief equals D8.8 which is due at the end of the project (M36).

Figure 16: First Policy Brief.

3.16 Social Media

All partners are instructed to publish postings on BioReCer information, activities, results and events via their own companies' Social Media channels (mostly LinkedIn and X). These posts should always include #BioReCer and related hashtags and the link to the project's website. Furthermore, all project partner institutions and the European Research Agency (REA) should be tagged. Also, all LinkedIn posts should be reposted in the project's groups, i.e. BioReCer – Biological Resources Certifications Schemes and the group shared with other certification projects, i.e. Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU BioEconomy (more information on the latter can be found in chapter 5: Synergies with Related EU Projects).

Furthermore, every partner are advised to repost in dedicated other LinkedIn groups, e.g.

- Agricultura España
- Bio-Based Economy
- BioReCer – Biological Resources Certifications Schemes
- Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU BioEconomy
- Circular & Regenerative Economy (Zero Waste Recycling Reuse Sustainable Sustainability)
- Circular Economy
- Circular Economy and Sustainable Finance (4Zeros) Research Network
- Circular Economy Club (CEC)
- Circular economy community – Ellen MacArthur Foundation
- Circular Water Economy
- Economía Circular España
- Economía circular - revalorización de residuos de la agroindustria
- European Centre for Regenerative Agriculture
- Forest Management & Wood Sourcing
- Forest Products Society
- Gestion de la Sostenibilidad /Sustainability Management
- Gestion de la Sostenibilidad /Sustainability Management
- MAGO PRIMA Project
- Residuos Profesionales
- Sustainability ESG CSR Climate Carbon Renewable Eco Green Net Zero Circular
- Regenerative Economy
- Water and Wastewater Treatment Professionals, Worldwide

- Water Treatment Industry Group
- Women in Cleantech and Sustainability

To support the project partners, EURADIA frequently prepares social media texts (in English and Spanish) and also provides custom-made imagery that are shared via the project’s GoogleDrive. These post texts inform about BioReCer and serve as invitation for stakeholders.

Up to date, about 500 (M1-18) Social Media posts have been published by all partners. Furthermore, a survey was published in the BioReCer LinkedIn group to decide on the setup of a potential glossary/FAQ section for the project website.

Figure 17: The BioReCer LinkedIn group (left), the online survey shared in the BioReCer LinkedIn group (middle) and an example for a Social Media post by a partner (right).

3.17 Horizon Europe (HEU) Instruments

In order to introduce and spread the generated knowledge and instruments, BioReCer will also actively include and utilise the pathways provided by the European Commission. This includes the publication of all deliverables and publications on the project EU-CORDIS site, but also technology boosting instruments like the Horizon Results Platform, The Horizon Europe Innovation Radar and the Horizon Magazine (for the latter a publication is planned in cooperation with related projects). Whenever possible, Horizon Europe and associated organs will be informed, tagged and actively involved in communication and dissemination measures through direct messages or social media related tags, in order to utilise their wide reach and broad network.

BioReCer participated in a Twitter campaign of the Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD) during the UN World Water Day (22nd March 2023). BioReCer's tweet informed about the project by tagging DG RTD (@HorizonEU).

In every SocialMedia postings the hashtag #HorizonEU or #HorizonEurope is used and the European Research Agency (REA) is tagged.

4 Dissemination Activities (M1 to M18)

4.1 Scientific Publications

In the course of the project, six publications are foreseen (i.e. three peer reviewed publications in high-impact scientific journals and three industrial publications in trade magazines). Seven publications were published by USC in Gold Open Access in 2023:

1. Arias, A., Feijoo, G., Moreira, M.T., 2023. Biorefineries as a driver for sustainability: Key aspects, actual development and future prospects. *J. Clean. Prod.* 418, 137925. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.137925>
2. Arias, A., Ioannidou, S.M., Giannakis, N., Feijoo, G., Moreira, M.T., Koutinas, A., 2023. Review of potential and prospective strategies for the valorization of coffee grounds within the framework of a sustainable and circular bioeconomy. *Ind. Crops Prod.* 205, 117504. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.indcrop.2023.117504>
3. Arias, A., Costa, C.E., Feijoo, G., Moreira, M.T., Domingues, L., 2023. Process modeling, environmental and economic sustainability of the valorization of whey and eucalyptus residues for resveratrol biosynthesis. *Waste management*, 172(1): 226-234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.10.030>
4. Arias, A., Costa, C.E., Feijoo, G., Moreira, M.T., Domingues, L., 2023. Environmental and techno-economic assessment on the valorization of vine-side streams to produce resveratrol. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 429, 139622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.139622>
5. Arias, A., Costa, C.E., Feijoo, G., Moreira, M.T., Domingues, L., 2023. Resveratrol-based biorefinery models for favoring its inclusion along the market value-added chains: A critical review. *Science of the Total Environment*, 168199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.168199>
6. Arias, A., Feijoo, G., Moreira, M.T., 2023. Advancing the European energy transition based on environmental, economic and social justice. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 43(12). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.10.013>
7. Lago-Oliveira, S., Arias, A., Rebolledo-Leiva, R., Feijoo, G., González-García, S., Moreira, M.T. Monitoring the bioeconomy: value chains under the framework of life cycle assessment indicators. *Cleaner and Circular Bioeconomy*. In press

At least five more publications are currently underway. All publications will be made available through the free online repository Zenodo and on the project website.

Figure 18: Two of seven BioReCer publications.

4.2 Events

4.2.1 Participation in Events

To date, all project partners participated in 20 different events such as conferences, workshops and trade fairs. The presentation of BioReCer in different events opens up networking opportunities and allows for recruitment of stakeholders of relevant communities, such as industry, science and policy for the BRSP. Event participation further enables dissemination of project outcomes, results and methodologies to make them available for exploitation.

The events, BioReCer partners have participated in are the following:

- 11.10.22 UNITELMA: Organisation of a workshop at Il Festival dello Sviluppo Sostenibili 2022 (The sustainable development conference)
- 11.10.22 UNIVPM: Participation in a workshop at Il Festival dello Sviluppo Sostenibile 2022
- 15.02.23 MEO: Participation in the 13th ISCC Sustainability Conference
- 23.05.23 NOVA: Presentation at the conference exhibition of the Renewable Materials Conference 2023
- 14.02.23 CETAQUA: Participation in a mobilisation and mutual learning workshop by EuBioNet and BioReCer's related project SUSTRACK.
- 17-19.04.23 UNIVPM: Participation in a trade fair: ECOMONDO Mexico
- 18-19.04.23 UNIVPM: Participation in a Workshop at El Centro de Investigación y Asistencia en Tecnología y Diseño del Estado de Jalisco, A.C. (18th to 19th April 2023 in Mexico)
- 23.05.23 MCS: Participation in the ISCC Certification body meeting (23rd May 2023): This is an internal closed meeting between ISCC and CBs associated with ISCC regarding sharing of information, updates and addressing queries. A slide on BioReCer was presented to inform certification bodies on participation of BRSP.
- 01-02.06.23 USC: Participation in the Renewable Resources and Biorefineries Conference (in Riga, Latvia)
- 06.06.23 MCS: Participation in the ISCC 7th Technical Stakeholder Meeting – Circular Economy and Bioeconomy (6th June 2023).
- 09.06.23 Several project partners: Participation in an online workshop organised by BioReCer's related project SUSTRACK.
- 20.06.23 NOVA: Promotion of BioReCer in an online NOVA session on Sustainability Certifications for the Circular Bioeconomy: Bio-based and CO₂-based circular solutions – how to ensure sustainable sourcing of non-fossil feedstocks?
- 21-24.06.23 CERTH and USC: Participation in the 10th International conference on solid waste management / CHANIA 2023 (in Chania, Greece)
- 26-29.06.23 USC: Participation in the 6th WA International Conference on eco-Technologies for Wastewater Treatment (in Girona, Spain)
- 24-28.07.23 USC: Participation in the International Conference of Life Cycle Assessment in Latin America (in Chile)
- 29-30.09.23 UNITELMA: Project booth at the European Researchers' Night organised by Frascati Science Association
- 20-22.10.23 UNITELMA: Participation in the Maker Faire - the European Edition (in Rome, Italy)
- 24-25.10.23 USC: Participation in the IFIB – International Forum on Industrial Biotechnology and Bioeconomy (in Florence, Italy)

- 05-08.11.23 UNI: Participation in the Biowaste: XXV Conference on Composting and Anaerobic Digestion accompanying the Ecomondo Exhibition (in Rimini, Italy)
- 09-12.11.23 USC: Participation in the Global Cleaner Production Conference (in Shanghai, China)
- 12-13.12.23 NOVA: Project booth shared with the related project 3-CO at the European Bioplastics Conference (in Berlin, Germany)

More events will be attended by the project partners in 2024 including the Renewable Materials Conference in Siegburg, Germany, and the Pollutec Paris.

BioReCer: Biological Resources Certifications Schemes

Aim: assessing and complementing current certification schemes for biological waste resources to enhance bio-based circular systems.

- 1.) A **multi-dimensional assessment framework** for biological waste feedstock and associated supply chains
- 2.) A **multi-agent approach** testing the framework in **four bio-based case studies** (forestry, fisheries, agriculture, municipal waste)
- 3.) **Complementing current certification schemes** including new criteria for sustainability, origin and traceability of biological resources.

Become a member of the **BioResources Stakeholders Platform (BRSP)!**

- Workshops and **brainstorming sessions**
- **Annual meetings**

→ **assessment of the framework and the BioReCer ICT tool, participation in development of guidelines for certification**

BioReCer receives funding from the Horizon Europe framework programme under the grant agreement number 101060684. Funded by the European Union.

Figure 19: Promotion of BioReCer in a workshop on certification organised by NOVA.

4.2.2 Organisation of Events

Besides the focus group discussions organised by the case study leaders (see D4.1 Report on the whole development of the BRSP), three more events had been organised by the BioReCer partners, including stakeholder events for the BRSP:

- 23.10.23 BRSP: Stakeholder Event in Greece (in person in Thessaloniki)
- 13.11.23 BRSP: Annual stakeholders meeting (online)
- 14.12.23 UNI: In cooperation with the related project Star4bbs, organisation of an online training on standards and R&I projects: How to support the bio-based industry

In June 2024 the stakeholder event in Sweden is to be organised as well as an Italian stakeholders event in autumn 2024. In late autumn/beginning of winter, the second annual stakeholders event will take place.

14th December – online, 15.00 to 17.00 (CET) – TRAINING ON STANDARDS AND R&I PROJECTS: HOW TO SUPPORT THE BIO-BASED INDUSTRIES

Don't miss this free-of-charge online training by UNI Italian Standardisation Body in cooperation with BioReCer's related project **Star4bbs!** The aim of this training is to shed light on the standardisation world: how it works, which are the main actors, and how it links with certification. The training will also highlight how organisations can transform R&I results into a fast-track standardisation document, the CEN Workshop Agreement – CWA. Finally, this training will explore standardisation outcomes from Star4bbs, BioReCer and Bioradar, and will disseminate objectives and intermediate results to companies, research institutions and standardisation experts.

REGISTER HERE to receive the programme of the training and the link to join.

For more information please contact **Cristina Di Maria**

Figure 20: Training action on standards by UNI in collaboration with the related project Star4bbs.

4.2.3 Workshops and Training Actions

Within WP8 (T8.2.3) three workshops for training actions/user testing is foreseen. These training actions should preferably be carried out in connection with WP4, WP5 and WP6, e.g. to evaluate the BIT after testing by the relevant stakeholders in the BRSP. At the consortium meeting in Thessaloniki in September 2023, NOVA organised an internal workshop with the respective WP leaders to decide on the next steps for organisation. A preliminary timeline was agreed upon with a first internal workshop by CERTH to introduce the BIT to the consortium in April or May 2025, a first external workshop for the BRSP probably in June 2024, a second workshop on the BIT and stakeholder perception together with UNITELMA in autumn 2024, and one or more training actions either in late 2024 or in 2025. A final training action to evaluate the BIT is going to be organised at the end of the project.

Figure 21: Preliminary schedule of upcoming training actions.

4.2.4 Event Calendar

An event calendar was established by NOVA for the CDP which is also available as an Excel list on the project's GoogleDrive. It was first updated in August 2023; the second update is currently underway. The list informs about upcoming events (name, date, venue) that are relevant for BioReCer topics and stakeholders that might want to join the BRSP.

4.3 Zenodo

In order to follow the FAIR science approach and to ensure Open Access to all project related publications and materials (publications, presentations, conference proceedings, flyers, brochures, project video, scientific posters and other scientific schooling material) even after the project has ended, NOVA established a BioReCer Zenodo Community. This community is accessible here:

<https://zenodo.org/search?q=biorecer&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=bestmatch>

It is frequently updated with publications and C&D material developed for BioReCer so that DOI numbers are now available for each published object. Furthermore, Zenodo allows an easy transfer and integration of uploaded objects to the EC Cordis Portal of the BioReCer project.

Figure 22: The BioReCer Zenodo community.

4.4 EC Cordis Portal

Throughout the project duration, all C&D measures have to be documented and reported to the European Commission via the EU Cordis portal of the BioReCer project. Accordingly, all C&D activities from M1 to M18 are being uploaded to the EC portal.

5 Synergies with Related EU Projects

Synergies and collaboration between EU projects of the same or similar calls are highly recommended by the EU. Therefore, BioReCer contacted several EU projects for collaboration. Currently (2nd February 2024), 15 other Horizon projects and the BioRefine Cluster Europe agreed to become related projects/clusters of BioReCer. These projects are all displayed on the BioReCer related projects subpage of the project website: <https://biorecer.eu/related-projects/> These projects either address certification of biobased products, the circular bioeconomy or the issue of utilisation of organic waste as feedstock. BioReCer was introduced together with Star4bbs in a press release by NOVA on 30th September 2022.

The BioReCer project partners were involved in related projects as participants in workshops (e.g. in a focus group and a mutual learning workshop organised by SUSTRACK), as speakers in (digital) events (e.g. in an online training on standards in collaboration with the project Star4bbs), as participant in an online survey (by SUSTRACK) or with a shared booth at a conference (together with 3-CO at the European Bioplastics Conference 2023 in Berlin).

Furthermore, NOVA organised several online workshops with related projects and a subsequent survey in order to identify measures that several projects are interested to proceed.

In a meeting on 17th January 2024, four related projects (i.e. BioReCer, 3-CO, Star4bbs and SustCert4Biobased) decided to establish a shared LinkedIn group, which was set-up by NOVA. The related projects had noticed that there is currently no LinkedIn group dealing with certification of biobased feedstock/products. This was identified as a gap and an opportunity to make available the projects' results, goals and opinions to a targeted stakeholder audience. The relevant stakeholders that decide to enter the group (e.g. certification bodies, policy makers, bioeconomy) can now be addressed in a joined effort without competing for their attention. The projects abstained from the idea to name the group after the projects or their call, but to give it a more general name: **Certification and Labelling Schemes for the EU BioEconomy**. This is because the related projects expect more stakeholders to join if it has a more general name and does not simply refer to EU projects. Furthermore, the projects intended to found a LinkedIn group that remains relevant even after the projects have ended. It can be accessed here: <https://www.linkedin.com/groups/12968114/>

It was also agreed upon that related projects are tagged and that their hashtags are included in Social Media postings whenever appropriate.

In a meeting on 20th February, 8 related projects discussed the possibility and topics of a shared article in the Horizon Magazine.

A meeting with related projects organised by NOVA for a shared webinar series about bioeconomy will be discussed in the near future.

Figure 23: Social Media post tagging the related project WaysTUP! (left) and the shared LinkedIn group with related certification projects (right).

6 Evaluation of C&D Measures

6.1 Tracking of C&D Measures

In order to ensure a seamless documentation and monitoring of all partner activities, NOVA created a so-called ECAS sheet. This MS Excel worksheet allows to keep track of all C&D measures carried out by the project partners throughout the project duration. The sheet covers a variety of possible activities, e.g., conference participations, organisation of workshops, social media activities, press releases and various sorts of publications which are documented in a separate tab. It also estimates and monitors the audience numbers reached through these specific activities, divided in various relevant stakeholder groups. The assigning of stakeholder and audience groups is based on their own individual information, surveys or estimations.

Between M1 and 18 three ECAS-sheet collection periods had taken place. NOVA was responsible to collect all sheets by all partners and to merge them into a master sheet. All C&D measures were updated by NOVA in the EC portal every six months.

6.2 Status of Deliverables

All deliverables within WP8 that were due until M18 were finalised and uploaded to the EC portal without any delays. This leaves only two more WP8 deliverables to be finalised until the end of the project's runtime (M36), i.e. the final report on BioReCer communication & dissemination activities and the final policy brief.

An overview of all deliverables of WP8 is shown below.

Table 2: Overview over all deliverables of WP8, their formats, dissemination levels and due dates.

No.	Title	Lead	Form	Dis. Level	Due Date
D8.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	6
D8.2	Project Website	NOVA	DEC – websites, patent flings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	6
D8.3	Project Leaflet	NOVA	DEC – websites, patent flings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	6
D8.4	Project Video	NOVA	DEC – websites, patent flings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	18
D8.5	Mid Report on BioReCer Communication Activities	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	18
D8.6	First Policy Brief	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	18
D8.7	Final Report on BioReCer Communication Activities	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	36
D8.8	Final Policy Brief	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	36

6.3 Reach of Measures

The table below shows the stakeholders groups and the numbers of stakeholders reached by the performed C&D measures of BioReCer between M1 and 18. It needs to be indicated that the numbers of persons reached are not necessarily absolute but estimations.

Table 3: Reach of C&D measures.

Reached stakeholders	Number reached
Civil Society/General Public	2,622,178
Customers	1,787
Industry	174,309
Investors	2,081
Policy Makers	9,636
Press/Media	2,392
Scientific Community	71,656
Other	10,554

6.4 KPIs

To evaluate the overall performance of executed C&D measures, suitable KPIs had been created, which are listed in table 6 of the CDP. In the last Consortium Meeting in Thessaloniki, Greece, in October 2023, an update for the KPI list was suggested by NOVA and approved by the consortium. It can be found below.

Table 4: C&D measures, their foreseen KPIs and the state of fulfilment in M18.

Activity	KPI	Achieved in M18
Website	>100 visits/month	ca.13,000 visits/month
Social Media	>50 posts with >500 impressions	>500 posts; 77 with >500 impressions
Factsheets/ Project Newsletters	5 reaching >50 subscribers	1 Factsheet in 4 languages 3 Project Newsletters reaching 76 subscribers
Press Releases	min. 6 in English	6 Press Releases
Offline Materials	>2,000 flyer copies	>2,050 flyers distributed
Conferences/Fairs	min. 20 international events	20 events
Workshops/Webinars	min. 6 with min. 50 participants	1 Greek stakeholders event with 13 participants; 1 training on Standards by UNI together with Star4bbs with ca. 50 participants
OA Publications	6 (3 scientific, 3 industrial)	7 (Gold OA)
BRSP	min. 20 stakeholders	85 members
Events for BRSP	4 annual stakeholders meetings with 50 participants; several FGDs, 10-15 participants per case study	1 annual stakeholders meeting with 64 participants; 4 FGDs, 6-18 participants
Policy Briefs	min. 2	1 Policy Brief
Video	1 video, ca. 2,000 views	1 video released in M18
BIT	no KPI yet	

7 Outlook

Further C&D measures are planned for the next half of the project. These are measures that were defined in the GA and other measures that make sense in order to increase the reach and success of the project:

- An update of the brochure should a fifth international case study be included,
- The final policy brief (D8.8),
- At least four workshops and training actions for stakeholders and members of the BRSP will be organised by collaborating WPs, e.g. explaining and evaluating the BIT,
- At least two factsheets will be prepared, e.g. on waste as a resource and the BIT,
- The high number of Social Media posts will be kept up,
- More annual stakeholders events will be organised,
- The project newsletter (including more mini-interviews) will be sent out to subscribers ca. every three months,
- BioReCer will be presented at more events to gain more members of the BRSP,
- More publications are already in the making or even under revision,
- The website will continuously be kept updated.

The fulfilment of the deliverables, the planned measures and the planned KPIs will be presented in the final report on C&D activities, and their success in supporting the project results will be evaluated at the end of the project.

8 Conclusion

Between M1 and M18 a multitude of different C&D activities have successfully been performed. Although several KPIs defined in the GA and the CDP have been increased by the consortium, most of them have already been met.

The Social Media strategy proved to be successful since the number of subscribers increased after each project newsletter promotion. This is especially the case since all information posted by partner companies can now be shared in different target groups, the BioReCer LinkedIn group and the shared LinkedIn group with related certification projects. This increases the reach of BioReCer postings immensely.

The BRSP has also grown in numbers and shows an almost balanced gender ratio and great diversity in terms of countries of origin and interest in the four different case studies. Every time potential stakeholders were addressed by targeted measures, registrations on the website increased.

The foreseen workshops and training actions did not reach their targeted KPI, yet. This is because, most training actions could not take place before BioReCer results were available and before the BIT was set up and ready to be introduced to BRSP members. Therefore, most of the workshops and training actions will take place in the second half of the project. Concerning the dissemination of project results, many relevant scientific publications have already been published and more will be accepted in the near future.

In the second half of the project, more C&D measures are upcoming, e.g. the development of more factsheets, organisation of training actions, release of scientific and non-scientific publications, another policy brief, and a final dissemination event.

Up to this date, no risks for the reach of KPIs of C&D measures have been detected and all related deliverables had been fulfilled.

9 List of Abbreviations

ACN	Active Citizenship Network
BIT	BioReCer ICT Tool
BRSP	BioResources Stakeholders Platform
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
CERTH	Centre for Research and Technology Greece
CETAQUA	Centro Tecnológico del Agua
D	Deliverable
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EGM	Easy Global Markets SAS
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FAQ	Frequently Asked Questions
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
GA	Grant Agreement
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
MCS	Meo Carbon Solutions
MS	Milestone
NOVA	nova-Institut für politische und ökologische Innovation
OA	Open Access
R&I	Research and Innovation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
T	Task
UNI	UNI - Ente Italiano di Normazione
UNITELMA	Unitelma Sapienza
USC	Universidade de Santiago de Compostela
WP	Work Package

BioReCer colour codes and format templates

	<p>Yellow CMYK: 0/30/85/0 RGB: 250/183/40 HEX: #fab728</p>
	<p>Green CMYK: 75/0/100/0 RGB: 37/166/45 HEX: #25a62d</p>
	<p>Blue CMYK: 100/70/0/30 RGB: 0/60/124 HEX: #003c7c</p>
	<p>Grey CMYK: 25/0/0/55 RGB: 112/134/143 HEX: #70868f</p>

BioReCer Colors	
#000000 - Text/Background - dark 1	
#ffffff - Text/Background - bright 1	
#003570 - Text/Background - dark 2	
#e0e0e0 - Text/Hintergrund - bright 2	
#fab728- Accent 1	
#25a62d- Accent 2	
#003c7c- Accent 3	
#70868f- Accent 4	
#25a62d- Accent 5	
#25a62d- Accent 6	
#03c7c- Link	
#954f72 - visited Link	

Formatierung löschen
BRC_Cover_category 10 pt
BRC_Cover_Subtitle
BRC_Cover_Subtitle_2
BRC_Cover_table_8 pt
BRC_Deliverable reference number
BRC_Head Executive Summary,Annex
BRC_Header contents
BRC_Project funding no
BRC_standard
BRC_table content
BRC_table head
BRC_Title1
Standard
table_title_content
WP_standard
1 Überschrift 1,BRC_Header 1
1.1 Überschrift 2,BRC_Header 2
1.1.1 Überschrift 3,BRC_Header 3
Überschrift 4
Fett,BRC_bold_blue 10pt
Beschriftung,BRC_labeling
Verzeichnis 1,BRC_List of contents 1
Verzeichnis 2,BRC_List of contents 2
Verzeichnis 3,BRC_List of contents 3
Abbildungsverzeichnis,BRC_List of figures
Fußzeile,BRC_footer
Hyperlink
Kopfzeile,BRC_header

Figure 24: Important Styles and format templates